

Communication through Arts in the Age of Global Contemporary Societies

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Abstract

This article studies the development of Performing Arts in our modern societies. Considering Art as a means of connecting people, we study the way in which performances evolve and adjust to contemporary societal demands. Although globalisation unifies societies in economic, educational and cultural terms, we can see that human alienation becomes the reality of our times. On the other hand, modern technologies have been introduced to create ground-breaking ways of empowering communication between the Art and its artists, as well as between the Art and its audience. In this article, we observe the progress of modern societies in relation to the Arts and the way in which it has been influenced by following the worldwide trends, technological advancements and social needs. Cyborg performance art, performers with artificially augmented bodies, avatars and Second Life relationships, computer-generated or virtual bodies and cybernetic societies, are our tools for analysing the creative, artistic advancement of our global and sometimes lonely societies.

Keywords

Cyborg performance, virtual body, virtual societies, avatars, second life experience

Introduction

When we talk about globalization we usually mean the integration of regional or national economies into international ones. If the economy was not one of the most important factors that make “*the world go round*”, we could claim that globalization is the result of the human need to communicate with each other. Furthermore, we need to admit that the evolution, immediacy and speed of the progress of communication are few of the most vital achievements of our modern global societies.

To build a global economy, the countries of the world have cooperated in the creation of the suitable conditions for political, societal and cultural exchanges, at the same advancing the communication technologies. Nowadays, we can be proud that the knowledge and the speed of information exchange become more available and easier accessible to people than any other time in the past, i.e. when comparing to the 60’s, 70’s or even 80’s. The network technologies connect people, countries and continents. As the technology advances, the new means of expression used by the artists to communicate their thoughts to our contemporary world change as well. Someone could say that this advancement influences the ways that art and artists converse their ideas to the public. The concept of the Art in general changes as

well. We are more and more moving away from the Aristotelian and Platonian theory of art, which refers to the mimesis and the representation of reality (Aristotle, 335 BC; Plato, 380 BC). The concept of the Art became related to mastering the skills, and the way of communicating these skills is clearly connected to the technologies used by artists. What we may notice is that the integration of the Art and the Technology is an unavoidable result produced by contemporary societies to satisfy their current needs, the needs which are always cultivated according to their cultural level. Therefore, the merger of Art and Technology is an inevitable result that has been drastically increased by modern societies to meet the needs of consumer's and/or user's nowadays. For example, the industrial design, which is the creative process of defining goods' form and characteristics, is a very important artistic field that often determines the usefulness, quality and in many cases the consumption quantity of a product. Another example could be the issue of communication with respect to current sense of aesthetics. We mean by this the ability of modern technologies to alter our experience of existence in space-time and to create new perceptions of contact that define alternative ways of human coexistence, i.e. telematics or virtual reality environments.

The need of being together

At the beginning of the first half of the 20th century, only few years before the introduction of the network technologies, artists tried to connect people who were spread around the world. One of them, Allan Kaprow, with his project "*Hallo*" (1969), linked four locations in the Boston area (Giannachi, 2004) by using TV channel facilities. The artist, as the director of the project, could switch from one location to another by changing the channels, whereas people from distinct locations could communicate with one another. Kaprow's aim was to introduce a global medium, interconnecting continents, languages and cultures in one sociological mix.

The main message of this project was that somebody could connect with anybody else at a different location without boundaries. Similarly, Kit Galloway and Sherrie Rabinowitz created the "*Satellite Arts Project*" (1977) shown in Figure 1, in which remote dancers interacted on the same show.

At the beginning, they were separated by a split-screen and at the end they appeared to be together in a third space, not here and not there, but somewhere in-between (Chandler and Neumark, 2005). The artists, were able to create a virtual performance space by using the Chroma-key techniques. It was like a common land, for people (performers) who live or exist in separate locations. Sherrie Rabinowitz's comment about the key technique was that: "*we discovered in our previous research however, that while this technique was good at simulating solid people and objects that something else was much more sensual as a human-to-human experience when being together with the "other" or others in the composite-image space*" (Rabinowitz, 1977). The need of *being together* is perhaps the most inspiring starting point for many artists. It is a need, which probably other people feel too, but they have not found the way to express it yet. The necessity of being together and sharing something common or the need to create a home to share, can be found in many arts works from, e.g. La Fura Dels Baus, Builder's Association, Station House Opera and others. As Gaston Bachelard argues: a home is "*our first universe ... [our] first world*" (Bachelard, 1958).

We should remember that at that time the satellite was the most common means of transmitting live TV broadcasts across oceans. Hence, artists had to focus on dealing with long transmission delays over long distance networks. They performed several telecollaborative dance, performance, and music scores to determine what genres could be supported, trying to assess what new genres would emerge as intrinsic to this new way of being-in-the-world. Very soon after the "*Satellite Arts*", the same artists were the creators of

the project “*Hole in Space*” (1980) shown in Figure 2 (Electronic Cafe International, 2002; 18th Street Arts Centre, 2008).

This work was based on similar technologies and was facilitated by a satellite connection, which linked the New York with Los Angeles. Thanks to these technologies, one evening in November 1980, the pedestrians walking outside of the Lincoln Centre for the Performing Arts in the New York City and some others walking past “*The Broadway*” department store in the open-air Shopping Centre in the Century City, in Los Angeles, unsuspectingly faced each other via big screens. They could see, listen and talk to each other like they had met by chance on the same sidewalk. The project lasted for three days and during that time brought together friends, relatives and families that had not met for many years.

When internet facilities spread widely, theatre companies like Station House Opera, staged performances having their performers acting simultaneously in different countries or even on different continents. It was October 2004 when the Station House Opera, in collaboration with De Daders experimented with the internet technology combined with the digital picture for first time. The company with the project “*Live from Paradise*” performed simultaneously in three locations across Amsterdam. In May 2005, the same project staged with nine actors who performed together while they were apart. Some of them were placed in Birmingham, some others in Colchester and the rest performed in London. Nine people in three different cities performed together in one single production. “*Live from Paradise*” was a global internet project that broke new grounds in live performances. The show took place in three distinct locations linked by video streaming to create a simultaneous combined performance, telling a story that used cinematic language to create a fourth imaginary space. At each place, the audience witnessed a live performance where video projections coming from the other two venues were combined on a large screen. Even though some sound delays occurred during the performance, probably because of the connection, the experiment of this artwork was a very successful one. It was a thrilling moment for the audience when at the end of the performance the three audiences from three different cities were cheering and clapping; while at the same time could see each other through the video streaming projected on the screens. It was one of these wonderful moments which can make the spectator feel like he is everywhere, here or there, it does not really matter, because the entire universe is one place. Possibly this is how an artist understands the concept of the globalization or the idea of being together.

The “*Live from Paradise*” was like a preparation project for the “*Play on Earth*” (2006) (Figure 3), a transcontinental collaborative performance staged on three continents, in Singapore, Britain and Brazil. In this production three remote places were merged together to create a fourth imaginary world. Three audiences, in each of the countries, experienced the performance simultaneously.

The illusion of being together

During the same period, Paul Sermon’s Telematic experiments have culminated in projects, such as: “*Telematic Dreaming*” (1992), “*Telematic Encounter*” (1996), “*Picnic on the Screen*” (2009) and others. His projects were based on network technologies, outlining the idea of the coexistence in a virtual place. For example, “*Telematic Dreaming*” (Figure 4) was an installation, facilitated over the ISDN network, which connected two locations operated as a customized video-conferencing system.

The idea was to enable a visual communication between the users, offering at the same time the virtual pleasure of touching each other in a different, third illusionistic space. Two separate interfaces were positioned in two distinct locations. The same kind of bed was placed at both locations. The one of them was placed in a blacked-out space and the other one in an

illuminated space. The bed in the lighted room had a camera which was positioned directly above it, sending a live video image of the bed, and the person ("A") lying on it, to a video projector located above the other bed in the dark room. The live video image was projected down on to the bed with another person ("B") on it. A second camera, next to the video projector, was sending a live video picture of the projection of person "A" with person "B" back to a series of monitors that surrounded the bed and person "A" in the illuminated location. In other words, the telepresent image worked like a mirror, which reflected one person within another person's reflection.

We may notice that the general principles of the latter telematic projects, i.e. "*Hole in Space*", "*Play on Earth*" and "*Telematic Dreaming*" are very similar in terms of technology and the concept. In the first case, we witnessed the coalescence of two separate worlds. We could see two separate societies coming together, communicating with each other via screens. People who lived apart for many years could meet thanks to the advanced technologies available at that time. In the second case, we saw the merger of three continents, an artistic collaboration for a global performance which connected three audiences which gathered simultaneously to attend the same cultural event; a transcontinental shared experience.

It seems like there are no communication boundaries anymore. The geographical distances are not able to separate people anymore. People can coexist and collaborate no matter the continent on which they live. The fact of Being Together, even if only visually, is a technological achievement with positive cultural and social effects.

Observing the "*Telematic Dreaming*", we could see two people (the spectators who turned in to performers) who were watching each other, performing at the same time a virtual touch, whereas they were in separate rooms (inside the same building). Technically this idea can be applied to very distant locations as well; people can perform a virtual touch no matter where they are located. We are in front of a pivot, shared experience by two people with pivotal point the self-projection or the self-extension in a different space via digital images. Possibly we are facing the two options of the same coin: the need of being together and the illusion of being together. On the other hand, we might be witnessing the fact of a virtual togetherness, a relation which does not necessarily need a real contact. In Paul Sermon's project, the participants/spectators look like they do not intent to "*cross the screen*" to be able to touch. They rather experiment with the medium in a playful way trying to duplicate reality using the telematics technology. According to Jean Baudrillard:

the celibacy of the machine causes the celibacy of "Telematic Man". Precisely as he grants himself the spectacle of his brain and of his brainpower as he sits in front of the PC or word-processor, the "Telematic Man" gives himself the vision of his fantasies and of a virtual "jouissance" similarly like he sits in front of his "minitel rose". He expels "jouissance" or cleverness in the interface with the machine. The Other, the sexual or perceptive interlocutor, is never really directed towards-crossing the screen demands the crossing of the mirror. The screen itself is established as the point of interface. The interactive screen transforms the progression of communication, the connection between the one and the other, into a process of commutation, for example the process of reversibility from the same to the same. "The secret of the interface is that the Other is within it virtually the Same - otherness being surreptitiously confiscated by the machine" (Baudrillard, 1987).

What is certain at this point is that the merger of art, science and technology has already created another reality. Computer technologies and internet facilities turned the entire world in to a big community. People were very much connected before their separation. Technology

became the interface which brought people and societies together, while art is the provider of experience, emotions or illusions offered to its community.

From telematic realities to virtual ones

Nowadays the realities are often questionable. Catherine Belsey claims that “... *in offering realism, it paradoxically veils the real*” (Belsey, 2005). On the other hand, the real for one person does not always match with the real of the other one. For instance, in the traditional theatre we used to talk about the spectator’s identification with the character of the play. There is always “a certain level of emotional engagement and internal viewer adjustments or identification, which forms part of most art forms, including the Theatre ...” (Lovejoy, 2004). Moving away from the traditional performative arts we should take in account that “technology allows us an alternate space within which we can invent unique methods of telling stories, forming identities, and remembering” (Flanagan, 2000). Today we can identify ourselves with an avatar. We do not have to squeeze in to another real body any more, waiting for a couple of hours for the big moment of Catharsis, which might come or might not. There is always a “Second Life” for us, where all the dreams may come true (Figure 5). Virtual realities can be real for some people and/or way of living for some others.

“Escape to the Internet’s largest user-created, 3D virtual world community”. This is how the *Second Life* (created in 2003) virtual world welcomes its visitors. “Who will you meet in *Second Life*? Who will you be? What will you discover? Everything is possible in the *Second Life*. Expect the unexpected. A whole new world is waiting” (Fluijt, 2011).

Second Life, is a virtual world partly created by its users. It is a virtual society with its own monetary system and recently faces a kind of recession. Currently, at any given moment, approximately 80.000 people are logged in. Everyday there is about 1.3 million USD (=208 million Linden Dollars) changing hands in transactions in this virtual world (Rountree, 2009). The avatars, that inhabit this on-line society, can teleport or fly or reside in a house, go clubbing, attend classes, create or view art, or spend time in a virtual environment, by sitting in front of a computer monitor. “*Second Life spans more than 42,000 acres in real-world scale. From press conferences and convention plenary sessions (Arrington 2006; NYLC 2006) to political speeches (Mistral, 2006), live musical performances (Campbell, 2007), and film debuts (Meyers, 2007), Second Life is a second home to over 2 million "residents," who collaboratively create, purchase, and comment upon its content. ...*” (Taylor, 2009). Unlike the actual life, museums, offices, classrooms etc are open (always virtually) 24 hours a day. There are avatars that represent people from all over the world, speaking different languages, and expressing multiple cultures and values. They are virtual people in a virtual world available for communication or collaboration. There are also more than 60 universities which teach classes in Second Life. There are at least 400 educators and researchers that exchange information on a key mailing list. There are also 4.9 million sq. meters of not-for-profit virtual ground with more than 75 islands (Wong, 2006; Taylor, 2009).

Art in our century develops and varies not only according to genre but also according to the medium of communication. The means of communication vary according to the financial, technological, social, educational, cultural level. Artists in the Second Life can create and exhibit work that they would not be able to produce in the actual life. A spectator or the viewer of a painting can travel inside of the canvas as seen in Figure 6 (Smith, 2010).

There are performances going on there, poetry and dance. Artists can meet in festivals, collaborate or perform together virtually; they can create and experience their team work regularly and much easier than the actual life. As Man Michinaga describes:

“... last week we were asked to intervene and set performance artist Stelarc on fire. Second Life is a videogame-like performance that makes one wonder about what is left in performance once you remove the body, which seems utterly ridiculous but it isn't because the affect remains. We really seem to feel through these puppets (avatars) of ours. The relational aspect of virtual worlds occurs through interaction with our audience or the creation of huge spectacles. The audience is free to do anything they wish. We invite participation. ... SL performance artists see immersion as a means of taking their art directly to a global audience, thus completely eliminating the need for physical exhibition spaces, although augmented reality exhibitions are becoming the norm” (Gaskins, 2009; Gaskins, 2010).

The truth is that the whole concept is a piece of Art. There is no doubt that the fusion of Art and Technology has created new worlds, more illusionistic than ever, far from the triviality of the everyday life. Even if the technology needs to be improved i.e. graphics, texts etc, the idea of being together or not to be alone is there and excites not only the artists but also thousands other people.

This game offers the option to choose who we want to be, the face and body that we want to inhabit, the profession and the society in which we prefer to live in. We can interact with the other or the others. We are allowed to experience relations with them that we would never have the courage to think of in the real life. We can buy houses and live a life not possible in the real world. We can get married and have a family or another family or another home. We can exist there as the other self. It can all happen without any danger or risk. We can safely sit in front of our monitor playing with our second self, or with our virtual child; i.e. remember the Natal project, *Milo*, Microsoft's virtual four-year-old boy, the artificial intelligence boy as shown in Figure 7 (Graham, 2010).

There are some people who spend more time in their “Second Life” than in their real one. It seems that this world offers the second chance in our first life. It looks like there is an opportunity here to repair one's life. Nevertheless, whoever wants to repair something needs first to admit its damage or malfunction. Whoever chooses to buy a second life is obviously not satisfied enough with his first one.

Creating artificial societies and virtual lives, through the collaboration between contemporary art and technology is one of the biggest achievements with ambiguous significance. Such types of 'so called “games” can offer not only a high-quality user entertainment, but be also a great research tool for scholars, researchers and business people who wish to experiment on future societies. For example, we can derive information about consumer's behaviour, new social trends, reactions to fashion and art, even test innovative working conditions of the employed people. We can use social games as a means of educating or treating people with various disorders etc. In such a way, we can statistically analyse results and propose new plans. Such “games” can be used, as it has been done already in many cases, as a unique group analysis engine producing results assorted by country, society, professions etc.

The question coming to mind is whether scientists and artists have merged their creativity to produce an innovative interpretational apparatus beneficial for our society, or they have offered a pure entertainment mechanism as an alternative solution to our insecure, stressful and ordinary life. Is the *Second Life* an inventive method for creating better and healthier worlds or is it just an escape from our real unwanted ones? *“It is true that some persons spend time in virtual worlds to be something different: women becoming men or men becoming women, adults becoming children, disabled persons walking, humans becoming animals, and so on. ... the degree to which an activity is “escapist” is independent of whether it is virtual or actual” (Boellstorff, 2010). “Naturally, the avatars ... in Second Life could not experience*

our real space...” As Johannes Birringer comments, what they experience is a more abstract modelled environment (Birringer, 2010). Benedict Anderson describes these communities as “imagined” ones because most of their members will never meet by chance one another; each of them believes that “*they all share some deep, trans-historical bond*” (Wegner, 2002).

Should we reconsider Jean Baudrillard’s statement about hyper-realities in which the difference between the man and a machine is difficult to be determined?

“The play has settled to one from screen to screen. It is almost dialogues between terminals or between different media. In a way, it is the medium conversing with itself, this intense circulation, this type of auto-referentiality of media which includes us in its network. But it’s somewhat of an integrated man-machine circuit. And at the present the difference between man and machine is very difficult to determine. ... you can never really go back to the source, you can never interrogate an event, a character, a discourse about its degree of original reality. That’s what I call hyper-reality. Fundamentally, it’s a domain where you can no longer interrogate the reality or unreality, the truth or falsity of something” (Gane, 1993).

Have we created a new realm where we can no longer distinguish between the real and unreal, the truth and the false of something? The *Second Life* is a perfect computer communication network, which puts thousands of people behind their computer screens, interacting with each other without any need to meet with one another, simply because none of them really exists and most of them would like to exist as an avatar. Many young people spend hours and days in front of their screens entertaining themselves by manipulating their second self in the “*Second Life*”. They would not interrupt this kind of pleasure if they did not have other obligations and duties that their real life requires them to perform. We may wonder if there is any reason for someone to abandon such a world if one did not have to face the functions and needs of one’s real body. The hunger and the reproduction are only two of many basic human needs. We may also wonder what kind of societies would be created if *Second Life* existed as our “*Second Chance*”. What kind of attitudes would we develop? Would we create a world like *Matrix*, *Gamer* or *Surrogates*? These movies demonstrate and illustrate ideas of aggressive control, not only over our own doubles/avatars, but belonging to others; avatars coexisting in the same world. How much can the fear of death influence development of our attitudes in our real and virtual lives? How much does the virtual life represent the real one? How difficult is it to accept the deterioration of the human body ... and the technological one as well? As we well know the machines can break down, fail to function properly, malfunction etc. There are viruses, created by humans that could completely destroy our artificial bodies. Hence, if we had a “*Second Chance*”, would we create a better place for living or would we duplicate the real one, just by adding more technology into it? What would become of us, the humans, if we were offered a “*Second Chance*”?

CYBORG PERFORMANCE AND THE IDEA OF BEING A GYBORG

Stelarc, known as a Cyborg artist, may be able to offer us an answer to the questions that we have asked before. According to him, as the body becomes obsolete we need to reposition it from the psycho realm of the biological sphere to the cyber zone of the interface, extending it by shifting from its genetic containments to an electronic extrusion. He claims that theories regarding evolution of species and gender distinction can be remapped and reconfigured for the alternative hybrids of the human and the machine. Hence an old-fashioned metaphysical distinction of the soul versus body and mind versus brain can be replaced by the disconnection between the body and species as the body is redesigned and diversified in its form and functions. Stelarc believes that as the old and often arbitrary psycho-analytical methods are exhausted, the obsession with the self, the sexual difference and the symbols will

start to subside in cyber systems that monitor, map and modify the body. ...“**cyber-systems spawn, alternate, hybrid and surrogate bodies**” (Bell and Kennedy, 2007). As he says, “*The question is not whether society will allow people freedom of expression but whether the human species will allow the individuals to construct alternate genetic coding. **The fundamental freedom is for individuals to determine their own DNA destiny***” (Bell and Kennedy, 2007) Stelarc claims that the evolution ends when the technology starts to invade the human body. By using miniaturised robots combined with nanotechnology we could have the option to become a host for the technology. By augmenting our body with these types of technologies we can enhance our bacteriological population. We can monitor it and strengthen it at the same time (Wood, 1999). On the other hand, and according to the artist’s ideas we could redesign the body by hollowing, hardening and dehydrating it. The example that he is using to sustain his argument refers to the process of giving birth. At the same time, he proposes a way to extend life or to avoid death. He notes that nowadays it is possible to create life outside the woman’s womb. We can fertilise the egg outside the body and re-implant it. Medically we could even sustain a foetus outside of the body. In this way, technically there would be no birth and the life would no longer begin with birth (Wood, 1999). He continues that if we can change or replace malfunctioning parts of the body with other accessible components, subsequently there should be no death, except in the case of any unpredicted terrible incident.

Although Stelarc’s ideas are very intriguing, strong contradictions in his thoughts might be more confusing than encouraging the creation of a better and longer living human body. As the artist admits, the technological invasion of the body will put an end on its evolution. This is a fact that we always assume to be unwanted. Stelarc’s argument is very much connected with the idea of extending life and avoiding death. However, by replacing body organs/parts with better ones we want to achieve a better quality of life and not just to extend the length of life of the humans. Various questions arise here. How much can a body live with replaceable parts? How much of the body enhancements can the brain accept? What about the compatibility among all the artificial components and their symbiosis with the brain? We know very well that brain does not work forever and it is structured to accept certain level of stress. It can also malfunction, age and crash similarly to a computer system. What is the next step then? Should we replace the brain when it starts malfunctioning? Even if we were able to do so, how would we replace this part of the body? Let’s assume that we could clone our brains and store them somewhere as backups for later use, like spare body parts. In this case we are talking about a total technological invasion of the body. Any further evolution of the humans would be based on digital technologies that may also malfunction. By creating this kind of humans or humanoids we automatically create new social conditions. The existence of the real human beings with the unmodified and hopefully healthy brains would be then necessary in order to control all the machinery around. This may sound like a Second Life game in which the player impersonates in flesh his Second Self.

Stelarc’s project “*Ping Body*” gives us a hint of what means for a human to control another human. In this project, he included ElectroEncephaloGram (EEG) for measuring brainwaves, ElectroMyoGram (EMG) for detecting currents associated with muscle contractions, plethysmogram for measuring changes in body volume, pulse meter and the Doppler blood flow meter. There were also other transmission devices and sensors monitoring the motion of his limbs, which signified his body posture. The performance of his body became a lighting installation, a kind of controlled choreography with movements which were constrained and involuntary. The artist transformed the spectator into a computer user. The viewer was able to remotely actuate Stelarc’s body by connecting to his WEB site and stimulating distinct parts of his body by clicking on his graphic image, an avatar. On the other hand, the artist could see

the person who was activating him by using ISDN Picture links and wearing goggles on his eyes. During the time when the viewer was activating Stelarc's limbs, he was involuntarily composing sounds and images in the performance space. Stelarc's body was equipped with sensors, electrodes and transducers on his legs, arms and the head that triggered body signals and sounds. The body was used as a video switcher and as a mixer that was stimulated by a computer. It seemed like Stelarc has reversed the relation between the human and the machine by being mechanically controlled by his users/puppeteers, who manipulated his body/puppet, involuntarily creating at the same time a unique scenography in space. On the other hand, the system took a control over the user from the moment that the spectator was producing unintentional effects that the performer was not able to control. The "*Ping Body*" was certainly an exciting and spectacular project; being such since it was a human's creation. We like such projects because they use technology in a totally innovative way. We are impressed with the inventive use of the new means, but this does not mean that we are ready to accept these projects as an alternative way of life.

As in the evolution of ideas there is always the next step, we cannot avoid here mentioning Kevin Warwick's opinion about the future human and the future societies. Warwick as a scientist and a researcher has been experimenting with extra sensual experiences by linking his nervous system with computers. He goes further than Stelarc, although he also sees human body as something obsolete and banal. In his book "*March of the Machines*" we can see how a scientist, and not yet an artist, thinks about our future. Kevin Warwick describes the year 2050 like that: our lives will be run by machines and we, the labourers, will have to do whatever they have planned for us to do. There is a scenography at this part, as he pictures the humans, who have very low communication skills, to carry out some work tasks, over rough land or to climb into irregularly shaped spaces. "*Physically the labourers are gelded, to cut out the unnecessary sex drive, and brains have been trimmed to avoid some of the human negative points such as anger, depression and abstract thought*" (Warwick, 2004). Most of the humans are males, or at least they used to be, and there are few particularly strong females that sometimes are used. Human genders have been destroyed and some unnecessary glands have been taken away. All of them look quite similar. The labourers are not required to worry and by removing such kind of feelings from their brain they need a good eight hours sleep, fortunately during night time, when their vision system performs poorly. Very often when they get near to the end of their useful working lifespan, it presents a good opportunity to get rid of the old stock. "*A labourer's working life starts at the age of about 12, having been selected at birth for such a role. By, about 18, labourers are at their peak of usefulness, and by about 27 or 28 they are usually worn out and are taken to incinerator, though some particularly strong humans do last until their 30's*" (Warwick, 2004).

If Kevin Warwick's ideas were staged as a performance or a theatre project we, the audience, would probably choose to identify ourselves with the machines. According to his scenario, they live longer, they are well served by their modified labourers and they are not in the danger of being incinerated when they are about to worn out.

CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we presented examples of contemporary artistic approaches where technology forms an integral part of Arts. Since artistic creations seem to offer less restrictions than when applied to everyday life, these technologies are used to the extreme interfering directly with human bodies and in turn creating dangers to creating similar changes to the human psychology. We lead the reader from Telepresence and Telematic technologies through to the Cyborg Theatre. We demonstrated through examples of the most representative artists that the fascination with technology may be a dangerous affair leading to alienation of the person as a

human being without any guarantee for resolving any inherent faults of the human bodies, like aging and death.

We cannot argue that the presented ideas are not very interesting and going beyond mere thoughts of the individuals, but they become also socio-political statements. For example, worlds described by Kevin Warwick resemble those dreamed of by Hitler in the 30s, almost a century ago, in which lower species are to serve the higher ones or, if not sufficiently useful, to be turned into ashes. There is also no need of using the common arbitrary psychoanalytical readings to realise that our anxiety about death is possible to turn us into a dead society with totally alienated people. Enhanced bodies can also malfunction, because computer systems malfunction as well. We do not know any computer system that has never crashed, at least until nowadays. There are no guaranties that such a system is ever going to be created, not even in the very far future. Better quality computers or implants can create distinctions between species. They can create the advanced species with good qualities in contrast to the other, lower quality creations that malfunction easier, the labourers. We are talking again about distinction of status. We are coming back to the same societies with even more alienated ex-humans. Furthermore, if it is so important to erase the sex from the human body, then why not just stop using it. This sounds very sad that to improve our bodies we have first to torture them by operating them and alternating them.

It is true that merging Art with the Technology improves both of them. It is a fact or a necessity that comes from and with the evolvement of our contemporary societies. We cannot stop such an improvement and we should not do it. Creativity and research are the most important components for any progress, cultural and scientific one. On the other hand, it seems sometimes that we are losing our goals not only as artists but also as recipients in front of a spectacle. Sometimes Art has been used to refer to any skill or mastery whilst other times this term has been related to the creation of an experience that can be shared with others. In any case, and without trying to create a cast for the concept of Art, we should admit that we are talking about a communication tool; a tool which converses ideas, thoughts and sometimes maybe also emotions. We see technology and machinery as a painter's contemporary brush or as the author's co-narrator. Observing a robot dancing or singing can still be exciting because it is a spectacle created by a human artist. That is one of the reasons that we love puppetry. But the manipulation of a Cyborg, a human by another human or a Cyborg (it does not really matter), sounds more sad than artistic. It looks more like a technological show than a Performance Art. Such a show can still be entertaining because releases its audience from any emotions as it is concentrated more on the idea of the technological improvement than on the real human and banal world. And at this point we might be diverting from our original goals. We have concentrated on the means that we use instead on what we really want to talk about, if there is anything still to be said as post-humans.

It might be easier to keep creating art if we are not sure of how to deal with our progress as humans. It might be easier to keep creating illusionistic worlds where we can erase or implant our sex, where we can construct and destroy the entire world in one instant, where we can create our Gods and semi-Gods. And after the show is over we could start planning for the next adventure. This is equally amazing.

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